

PLANT GROWTH-PROMOTING FUNCTIONAL REPERTOIRE OF ENDOPHYTIC *ARTHROBACTER PSYCHROCHITINIPHILUS* AND ITS GENES *IN VIVO* EXPRESSION IN ANTARCTIC VASCULAR PLANTS

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The impact of endophytic bacteria on Antarctic vascular plants is one of the essential survival factors for the growth of *Deschampsia antarctica* and *Colobanthus quitensis* under extreme environmental conditions. Plant microbiome enhances adaptation owing to the activity of plant growth promotion genes. This study aimed to investigate the Antarctic endophyte genome and analyze the expression of its PGPT genes in the inoculated plants *D. antarctica* and *C. quitensis*.

Based on our previous study endophytic bacteria *Arthrobacter psychrochitiniphilus* 15.6 that affected the growth of plants was selected for a whole genome sequencing. The chosen bacterial strain was isolated from the leaves of *D. antarctica* collected on Ronge Island. The sequencing was performed by Illumina NovaSeq 6000 with a sequencing depth of 7 Gbp. The genome sequence of *A. psychrochitiniphilus* 15.6 was quality-checked by FastQC, Version 0.12.1, and assembled by Unicycler, Version 0.5.1. The quality of the assembly was estimated by Quast, Version 5.3.0. Genes' annotation was conducted by eggNOG-Mapper, Version 2.1.8.

Genes' analysis was focused on the crucial plant growth promotion traits: modulation of environmental stresses and phytohormones production. From the genome annotation of *A. psychrochitiniphilus* 15.6 trehalose synthesis genes (*otsA*, *otsBI*, *otsB2*), glutathione peroxidase synthesis gene (*btuE*), and tryptophan synthesis genes linked to indole acetic acid (IAA) production (*trpC*, *trpD*, *trpE*, *trpF*) were found. For all selected genes, specific primers and thermal conditions for PCR analysis were designed by Oligo Primer Analysis, Version 6.31, SnapGene Viewer, Version 6.2.1, and Primer-BLAST in the NCBI database.

For the inoculation assay, plants of *D. antarctica* collected from Irizar Island (Argentine Islands) and *C. quitensis* from Cap Rasmussen (Kyiv Peninsula) were used. Antarctic vascular plant specimens were cloned *in vitro* and after the inoculation with the bacterial suspension *A. psychrochitiniphilus* 15.6 were divided for incubation at separate conditions. One group of each species was incubated at +10°C and another group at +4°C.

As a consequence of the inoculation with Antarctic endophyte, the effect of low temperature on plants as a stress factor was reduced. Bacteria *A. psychrochitiniphilus* 15.6 contributed to cold adaptation. The expression of genes *otsA*, *otsB*, *trpC*, *trpE*, *btuE* *in vivo* in plants was detected by PCR analysis. *In vivo* expression of these PGPT genes can contribute to stress adaptation and growth enhancement of Antarctic vascular plants.

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